

Research Article

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A Linkage Between Perceived Corporate Image and Organisational Identification in the Banking Sector in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Whether an organization makes an effort to change its image, every organization has one. The stakeholders' perceptions of a particular firm activity as well as related global and industry challenges shape the perceived corporate image. One of the important topics in the management and organizational fields has been corporate image. The study's goal is to investigate the relationship between organizational identity and perceived corporate image. The study used a survey methodology to gather the data, which was then analyzed using IBM SPSS version 21.0's arithmetic mean, correlation, and regression functions. The study found that the notion of perceived corporate image is one of the fundamental ideas for being relevant and competitive in a globalized company environment. The link between perceived corporate image and employee engagement was examined in two distinct dimensions, external and internal, each with its own set of values. According to their own social responsibility ideals, an employee who believes that their company is renowned because it practices social responsibility may be more (or less) inclined to report involvement. Additionally, based on the study's findings, it was determined that there is a strong positive association between perceived internal and external image and organizational identity, and that both of the perceived corporate image's sub-dimensions had a favorable impact on that relationship. Future research might evaluate if, and to what extent, organizational culture influences corporate image and organization identity, according to the study's recommendations.

Introduction

Management of corporate image is clearly a concern for organizations. This demonstrates that attitudes about an organisation and pro-corporate supporting behaviours are strongly positively correlated. The mental representations of a company are said to be represented by corporate images. We refer to the corporate image as the whole of these perceived qualities of the company.

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Regardless of what the company accomplishes, every organisation has a certain image. The stakeholders' impressions of certain firm act as well as relevant global and national concerns influence corporate image. Stakeholders' perception of an organization greatly affects how they will respond to particular company activities and goods.

Corporate image has recently been one of the important topics in the management and organizational fields. Organizations are obliged to take projecting a favorable image in front of all stakeholders and the fact that it has been a crucial factor influencing organizational life via long-term partnerships into consideration, especially given the competitive climate of the modern day. A strong company reputation is necessary for business connections. Every action done and every choice made by businesses has an indisputable influence on workers, service customers, business partners, rivals, and eventually all internal and external stakeholders in the business sector where the effects of globalization are felt most strongly. However, stakeholders can predict an organization's future by forming an opinion of it based on the statements and actions of the organization. According to Olins (1999), corporate image is a phenomenon made up of beliefs, opinions, feelings, and knowledge associated with a company as a result of all of its operations. In this sense, a company's image goes beyond its name or emblem. Instead of a company's name, corporate image is thought of as the opinions and perceptions of parties both inside and outside the business (Abratt, 1989). Information and inferences regarding the company's reputation as a client, supplier, consumer, member of the community, and employer are part of its corporate image. Since an organization's corporate image influences the behavior of stakeholders, they work to develop and manage their image for a variety of reasons, including: 1. Increasing the corporate competitive advantage, which increases profitability; 2. Fostering positive relationships with the community in which they operate; and 3. Avoiding difficulties with hiring, selecting, and maintaining employee morale. influencing financial institutions and investors.

However, while not a novel idea, organizational identity has been a crucial variable in studies of organizational behavior. In this sense, organizational identification has been defined as a "desired link" between an individual and their organization by scholars and practitioners (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Dutton et al., 1994; Whetten & Godfrey, 1998). In other words, organizational identification is defined as the level of fusion between a group's fundamental identifying traits and its members' individual identities (Dutton et al., 1994).

Corporate image as viewed by workers has a significant influence on organizational identity, according to organizational theorists. According to pertinent research, the corporate image creates a psychological bond between employees and a business and enables employee identification by fostering teamwork and a sense of organizational trust. Numerous studies reflecting on how people see companies, their level of loyalty and commitment, people's directions in life, and their desire to continue working for their company are used to analyze the identification notion in the literature (Smidts et al., 2001; Ashforth et al., 2008).

Statement of the problem

Organization theorists believe that employee perceptions about the organization's corporate image have a big impact on how people identify with the organization. According to the pertinent

literature, corporate image creates a psychological connection between an employee and a company, assures that workers identify with their organization, and increases employee collaboration and organizational trust. Numerous studies that study the idea of identification, what an organization means to people, how engaged and committed people feel toward organizations, and people's propensity to stick with them can all be found in the literature.

An earlier study suggested that external image had a greater organizational impact on businesses with better identity, recognition, and image in line with communication climate. On the other hand, it has been claimed that organizations with low recognition have a more favorable communication atmosphere. It is important to look into how corporate image is influenced by how socially well-known an organization is to those outside the organization. Examining how perceived corporate image affects organizational identification level is also crucial. This is the study's underlying assumption.

Objective of the study

The study's goals are to identify the relationships between internal and external corporate image and organizational identity, as well as to evaluate the link between perceived corporate image and organizational identification.

Propositions

H1: Employee perception of the external corporate image does not raise their degree of organizational identification.

H2: Employee perception of an internal corporate image does not raise their organizational identification level

H3: There is no meaningful connection between organizational identification and the internal and external company image.

Literature review

Identification concept

It can be seen that the word "identification" has two different references in its lexicon: the first is the process of a person participating in the lives of others and sharing their emotions in a way that causes their personalities to coalesce; the second is the process of a person becoming aware of and describing oneself (www.tdk.gov.tr). In order for the identification phenomenon to emerge, a person must have a sense of likeness, belonging, and loyalty. Similarity refers to sharing goals and interests with other people. Membership refers to receiving social support so that one can have a sense of belonging. On the other hand, interdependence amongst people to support and defend shared goals and policies with others may be described as loyalty (Gautam et al., 2016).

The definition of the identity idea now causes some uncertainty. While some scholars (Albert et al., 2000; Haslam, 2016) combine organizational identification and identity into one meaning, others distinguish between organizational identification and identity (Dukerich, 2016). Similar to how some academics contend that organizational identification and commitment have the same meaning (Riketta, 2005), others argue that they differ from one another experimentally (Gautam et

al., 2004; Van Knippenberg & Hogg, 2018). In fact, internalization, commitment, and identification must all be distinguished from one another. Organizational identification is the "perception of individuals themselves together with their organizations and viewing success or failures of their organizations as their own" (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1986; Ashforth & Mael, 1989). This is the point at which identity can be distinguished from identity concept. Regarding the distinction between identification and commitment, it is possible to argue that while identification is more closely related to internal factors like sacrificing personal interests for the benefit of the organization or taking on additional roles within the organization, commitment is more closely related to external factors like attitudinal variables like job satisfaction (Ashforth et al., 2008).

Contrarily, Boros (2008) addresses the concepts of identification and internalization by drawing on research by Levinson (1991), Ashforth and Mael (1989), which shows that while identification is a concept of perception, internalization is the synthesis of norms that direct one's own behaviors, attitudes, and values as well as those of the group to which one belongs or nests. Furthermore, individuals may not necessarily recognise the ideals or attitudes of the social category they belong to on a personal level. Again, while identification suggests a special condition for the organization, internalization and commitment ideas may not be affected by this circumstance because of common aims and values. Each organization does really have unique organizational goals and values. A person may get committed as a consequence of a tool they made for their own professional aspirations, and they may leave their group for another one that better matches their own needs. In other words, people might switch from one social group to another to maximize their own gains. A member of a particular social group, however, cannot quit their organization without experiencing "spiritual loss" (Boros, 2008).

Organizational identification concept

An American political scientist named Lasswell utilized the identification idea in the literature for the first time to characterize the relationship between global policies and individual attitudes and behaviors (Lasswell, 1935). According to Lasswell, identification is a process that is directed by emotional ties that have been formed with other individuals and in which likeness perceptions emerge. He also said that such a bond could only develop because there are so many common relationships and symbols (Cheney et al., 2010; Tokgöz & Aytemiz Seymen, 2013).

Tolman describes the relationship between identification and group as that identified groups feel that they are part of them, and as a result, the future of the group becomes the future of the individual, the purpose of the group becomes the purpose of the individual, and success or failure. The organizational identification concept was first introduced to the literature by Edward Tlxrrgn as cited by Kose (2009), and defined as the "engagement of a person with a group which he/she feels like part of them" (Kose, 2009).

In essence, it is feasible to claim that organizational identity emerged when members of organizations began to define themselves in terms of their connections to those organizations (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Dutton et al., 1994). According to Ashforth and Mael (1989), organizational identification is "a cognitive structuring, harmony between values of organization and persons; or being part of organization or feeling of the person in the same entity with his/her

organization, feeling belonging" (i.e., coalescence of individual and his/her organization) or "cognitive engagement of the person with values and purposes of organization" (Buchanan, 1974).

Following organizations' examination of Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1985), the identification notion was presented in the pertinent literature from a fresh perspective as "shared identity" in the 1980s (Ashforth & Mael, 1989;). According to Boros (2008), the most notable development in social sciences over the past 20 years has been the use of social identity theory to address the idea of identification. According to Tajfel (1982, p. 2), who draws his definition of identity from this theory, identity is "a component of the social environment of an individual that results from personal knowledge, membership in a social group or groups, and their commitment to this membership in terms of sense and values."

On the other hand, Bartels highlights Tajfel's (1982) claim that a person's identity is determined by both their group or organization of affiliation and their personal traits. Being a member of a group implies that the individual shares some of the group's beliefs and ideals. Members' own identities and self-confidence are favourably impacted by this circumstance. Identification with organization is the functional step in this process introduced by membership in an organization through identity (Bartels et al., 2007).

According to Pratt (1998), who holds the same perspective, organizational identification occurs when an individual first begins to define himself or herself in terms of the identity of his or her organization and then under two other circumstances. Organizational identification creates a mental link between an individual's self-definition and the definition of his or her organization through influencing attitudes, behaviors, deep affects, and cognitive processes (Dutton et al., 1994; Edwards, 2005).

By asking themselves, "Who am I in terms of the relationship between my organization and me?," people who are associated with their organizations create a strong sense of self and set themselves apart from others. On the other side, employees who identify with their companies work harder to support them and acquire key attitudes and behaviors like loyalty to the organization and appreciation (Wiesenfeld et al., 1999; Miller et al., 2000; Smidts et al., 2001).

Increasing concord and congruence between an organization's goals and that of its members is another definition of organizational identity (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). In other words, when people identify with their organization, they at least somewhat personalize that organization (Ashforth & Mael, 1998). Organizational involvement, on the other hand, largely replaces the idea of organizational identity. As was said above, some scholars believe that identification and engagement have the same meaning, while others believe that identification is a component of engagement.

Concept of image

Sidney Levy initially described the image idea in 1955 as the "aggregate of belief, attitude, and impressions of individuals and groups towards specific themes." Since then, it has been used to a variety of topics and its scope has been enlarged (Barich & Kotler, 1991). Generally speaking, an image concept was defined as "positive or negative opinions about a subject or asset whose

occurrence depends on the interaction of factors in people's minds and time." As a result, image concepts have begun to be seen as being applicable to political candidates, products, or entire nations. It was highlighted that the overall impression generated in someone's mind, rather than the conduct or quality of a person or object, is what matters most at this stage (Dichter, 1985).

Although the terms "image" and "identity" have occasionally been employed in different contexts, it is not reasonable to assume that they have the same meaning. Organizational identity has a distinct connotation than the corporate image, which also contains organizational identity. When seen from the perspective of an organization, identity is valued. On the other hand, image relates to the value perceived by others around you. The image relates to how a company is viewed by the public; in other words, it refers to how people feel about a company.

Despite the fact that many scholars have looked at organization identity (Gray & Smeltzer, 1985; Dorgan & Schatzkin, 1991); a study by Lambert (1990) offers a robust model in this area. While Lambert (1990) viewed organizational identity from an "iceberg" perspective, he made an effort to highlight two defining qualities of identity that help us separate it from an organizational image. Identity was first defined as the providing of all outward manifestations that set an organization apart from others and was compared to the tip of an iceberg. In this instance, the organization's brand, logo, and colors were mentioned as the tip of the iceberg; organizational identity merely refers to an organization's public face.

Theoretical framework

Kotter's change model was initially released in 1995 following research on effective organizational change initiatives. He created an eight-stage method for large organizational transformation based on the idea that change within an organization is difficult to achieve (Kotter, 1996). The eight stages are: (1) creating a sense of urgency; (2) forming the guiding coalition; (3) formulating a vision and a strategy; (4) communicating the change vision; (5) empowering widespread action; (6) producing short-term wins; (7) consolidating gains and producing more change; and (8) enshrining new methods in the culture. These actions can facilitate an effective shift in a variety of organizational circumstances (Kotter, 1996). Establishing a feeling of urgency is the first stage in bringing about significant change. In this phase, businesses must evaluate their product delivery rigorously and look for areas for development. Eliminating complacency is a crucial part of this phase; everyone in the company needs to be motivated to do better. A steering coalition must then be established. People with positional authority, knowledge, credibility, and leadership should be part of the governing coalition. Trust is crucial at this point to prevent the change efforts from being thwarted. The organization must next create a vision for the transformation and tactics to address it. Introducing the transformation vision is the fourth stage. If other members of the organization are unfamiliar with the vision, it is ineffective. Before the change really happens, the first four steps (forming the steering coalition, building a vision and plan, and conveying the change vision) take place. The first four phases in the transition process, according to Kotter (1996), "help thaw the status quo" (p. 22). For the change management process to work, the status quo must be broken and a window opened for change.

As Kotter (1996) outlined "Corporate image is the consumer's reaction to the entire product and is summed up from the public's perceptions of a company. This indicates that corporate image is defined as the number of beliefs, ideas, and impressions of individuals inside an organization. It also means that corporate image is the customer reaction to the whole product offered by one firm." Corporate image is defined as the total perception of a company in the public's mind. It has to do with the company name, the building, the range of goods and services, tradition, ideology, and the sense of quality each employee conveys when they deal with customers.

Therefore, one of a company's or organization's most valuable assets that have to be consistently developed and maintained is its image. A strong marketing tool and a positive reputation may influence customer satisfaction and attitude toward a business as well as draw customers to a product or service. Corporate image cannot be designed, which means that it is molded by society, communication, and transparency in the company's initiatives to develop the favorable reputation that is desired. Building a picture takes time and cannot be done randomly or only at particular periods. Because customers' perceptions of objects are constantly created via the processing of information from a variety of sources.

Empirical analysis

According to Riketta (2005), there is a conceptual link between affective involvement and organizational identity, which accounts for practice confusion. Whereas Riketta (2005) found weak correlations between organizational identification and job satisfaction, desire to continue in the job and discontinuance, and reported significant correlations between additional-role behavior and support and participation into job factors based on meta-analyses on organizational identification and organizational engagement (Ellis, 2008). Numerous additional studies in the literature found that when people perform above and above what is anticipated, the firm is more productive and profitable. This also enhances employee motivation and job happiness, which raises client satisfaction and loyalty (Ashforth et al., 2008).

The degree to which a person identifies with an organization in that organization reflects the degree to which that member is engaged with that organization. If an individual's affiliation with an organization occupies a significant place in their hearts and the significance of that affiliation has increased in comparison to other affiliations with other social groupings, then that individual has a strong sense of identity with that organization. Positive effects of employees' connection with their organization at both the individual and organizational levels have been stressed since high degrees of identification are notable in terms of their link with positive organizational behaviors (Witting, 2006; Ashforth et al., 2008).

The most studied topic in organizational identification studies is that choices are made inside organizations through teamwork and cooperation in order to promote organizational effectiveness (Simon, 1976; Tompkins & Cheney, 1985; Bartel, 2001; Ashforth et al., 2008). Organizational identification, according to March and Simon (1958, p. 65) and McGregor (1967, p. 145), blends individual and organizational goals and improves harmony between them. However, when organizational identification grows, Hall et al. (1970) underline that this circumstance would lead to dedication to organizational goals. Similarly, O'Reinelly and Chatman (1986) discovered that

employees have a psychological bond with their businesses, which enables them to see themselves as a part of it. Members of an organization become more devoted to it when they have a sense of belonging. On the other side, the internalization of norms and values by employees increases their desire and intention to remain in the firm (Wiesenfeld et al., 1999). The favorable relationships between identification and employee motivation, work satisfaction and job commitment, organizational citizenship, and other factors have also been the subject of multiple research (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1986; Knippenberg & Van Schie, 2000; Ashforth et al., 2008).

Methodology

The survey research design is the one that was used. This approach was chosen since it enables one to visit the area in question and get information firsthand. As a result, there is potential for generalization because it provides a representative sample of the population.

Study population and samples size

All workers of Nigeria's First Bank plc make up the population being studied in this study. The annual report for 2018 states that First Bank Plc. has 8540 employees.

This study's data came from both primary and secondary sources. The target respondents' responses to the questionnaires that were given to them served as the primary data source. The secondary sources are pertinent information obtained to assist the study from journals, articles (newspaper excerpts), bulletins, internet searches, and other published data sources.

Data collection instrument and design

Because the respondents were given options and asked to choose among them, this study incorporated the use of a structured questionnaire.

Leading questions were avoided because of the way the questionnaire was designed. There were two parts to it. Section A focused on the respondents' biographical information. Questions that addressed the topic were the main focus of Section B. Basically, the multi-choice and Likert Scale questions in section B were designed based on study ideas.

Administration of research instrument

The researcher personally administered the instrument after obtaining institutions' consent*. Within two weeks, the questionnaire was provided to respondents at a few chosen organizations in Lagos State. A follow-up visit was performed one week later to retrieve the questionnaires that had previously been distributed.

Data analysis technique

Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics made up this portion (Statistical Analysis). In order to organize the data through Data Preparation, Tabulation, and Summarization, descriptive statistics were employed. These statistical measurements of central tendency and dispersion allowed certain interpretations and significant correlations that were buried within the data to be deduced with the use of inferential statistics.

Tables, graphs, and other formats were used to show the generated data. Histograms and basic frequency distributions make up some of the important analyses.

Regression analysis was used to examine various relationships between the variables, while inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to evaluate relationships between two variables. A 5% level of significance was used to examine the statistics. After entering the selected variables and the returned questionnaires into the program, statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. The data were checked for errors as part of quality control procedure, and the administered instrument also underwent the proper validity and reliability testing.

Results

Demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown in the table 1. According to the respondents' gender breakdown, a total of 137, or 57%, are women, while 104, or 43%, are men. Additionally, 80% of the respondents are married, while only 20% are unmarried. According to the respondents' age distribution, 37% of respondents are between the ages of 25 and 30; 29% are between the ages of 31 and 40; 20% are beyond the age of 40; and 13% are under the age of 25.

Table 1.

Demographic characteristics of the respondents (n=241)

		Frequency	Percent			Frequency	Percent
<i>Gender</i>	Male	104	43.2	<i>Highest Academic Qualification</i>	HND/B.Sc/B.A	114	47.3
	Female	137	56.8		M.Sc/MBA	127	52.7
<i>Age</i>	Below 25 years	32	13.3	<i>Years of working Experience</i>	1- 3 years	44	18.3
	25-30 years	90	37.3		4- 6 years	55	22.8
	31-40 years	70	29.0		7- 10 years	109	45.2
	Above 40 years	49	20.3		Above 10 years	33	13.7
<i>Marital status</i>	Single	49	20.3				
	Married	192	79.7				

According to the academic qualifications, 127 people, or 53%, had an M.Sc. or MBA, while the remaining 47% had an HND, B.Sc., or B.A. In addition, 45% of respondents had between seven and ten years of work experience, 23% had between four and six years, 18% had between one and three years, and 14% had more than ten years.

As shown in Table 2, a large majority of the respondents concurred that their employer's successes are also their successes ($M=3.89>3.00$), that they would be embarrassed if a media report criticized their employer ($M=3.72>3.00$), that it feels personal when someone criticizes their organization ($M=3.60>3.00$), and that they are very interested in what others think about their organization ($M=3.90>3.00$). They also frequently use the pronoun "we" rather than "they".

Table 2.*Organizational identification*

	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Remark
This employer's successes are my successes	3.00	5.00	3.89	0.74	Agreed
If a story in the media criticized this employer, I would feel embarrassed	1.00	5.00	3.72	1.09	Agreed
When someone criticizes this bank, it feels like a personal insult	1.00	5.00	3.60	1.10	Agreed
I am very interested in what others think about this organization	2.00	5.00	3.90	0.93	Agreed
When I talk about this employer, I usually say 'we' rather than 'they'	1.00	5.00	3.98	0.86	Agreed
When someone praises this employer, it feels like a personal compliment	1.00	5.00	3.87	1.06	Agreed

The majority of respondents, as shown in Table 3, agreed that their employer is among the best ($M=3.70>3.00$), that former employees would be proud to have their children work there ($M=3.99>3.00$), that someone looking to advance their career in this field of employment should downplay their association with their employer ($M=4.03>3.00$), and that when I'm at work, my mind is on my job ($M=3.91>3.00$).

Table 3.*Internal corporate image*

	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Remark
My employer is considered one of the best	1.00	5.00	3.70	0.96	Agreed
Former employees of my company would be proud to have their children work here.	1.00	5.00	3.99	1.03	Agreed
A person seeking to advance his or her career in this area of employment should downplay his or her association with my employer.	1.00	5.00	4.02	0.89	Agreed
At work, my mind is focused on my job.	2.00	5.00	3.91	0.83	Agreed

According to Table 4, the majority of respondents concur that their community and fellow citizens have favorable opinions of their employer ($M=3.72>3.00$) and that having worked for their employer in the past is seen as an honor in the neighborhood ($M=3.95>3.00$).

Table 4.*External corporate image*

	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Remark
People in my community think highly of my employer.	1.00	5.00	3.72	1.09	Agreed
It is considered prestigious in the community to be a former employee of my company	2.00	5.00	3.95	0.79	Agreed
People look down at my employer	1.00	5.00	2.02	1.06	Disagreed
My employer does not have a good reputation in my community.	2.00	5.00	1.96	0.92	Disagreed
When other employers are recruiting, they would not want employees from my company	1.00	5.00	2.14	1.06	Disagreed

However, the majority of respondents disputed that their firm is despised by the public ($M=2.02<3.00$), that their employer does not have a good reputation in the community ($M=1.96<3.00$), and that other companies would not want to hire workers from my company ($M=2.14<3.00$) when they are hiring.

Propositions

H1: As external Corporate Image Perceived by employees does not increase their organizational identification level increases, too.

Table 5.

Relationship between external corporate image and organizational identification

	N	Mean	Std. Dev. Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark	
External corporate image	241	12.64.	2.48	0.466**	0.000	Significant
Organizational identification	241	19.04	3.09			

***r -calculated => r-critical= 0.195; significant value (p) = 0.000<0.05

Table 5 showed that the mean response for organizational identity was 19.04 and the mean response for the external corporate image was 12.64. The Table further demonstrates the significance of the computed r of 0.466 at the 5% level. This suggests that organizational identity and external company image have a favorable and substantial link. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Proposition 2

H2: As internal Corporate Image Perceived by employees does not increase their organizational identification level.

Table 6.

Relationship between internal corporate image and organizational identification

	N	Mean	Std. Dev. Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark	
Internal corporate image	241	11.78.	3.12	0.653**	0.000	Significant
Organizational identification	241	19.04	3.09			

***r -calculated => r-critical= 0.195; significant value (p) - 0.000<0.05

Table 6 showed that the mean response for organizational identity was 19.04 and the mean response for internal corporate image was 11.78. The Table further demonstrates the significance of the computed r of 0.653 at the 5% level. This suggests that internal corporate image and organizational identity have a favorable and important link. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Proposition 3

H3: There is no significant relationship between corporate image (internal and external) and organizational identification.

In testing the hypothesis, Regression analysis was employed. The analysis is presented in Table 7.

Table 7.

Regression analysis showing combined influence of corporate image (internal and external) on organizational identification

Model	Dependent Variable	Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	t-value	Sig. P	R ²	DW	F
	Organisational identification	Constant	28.67	2.79	0.65	0.76			
1		Internal corporate image	0.68	0.23	2.99	0.01	0.76	1.78	10.89
		External corporate image	0.61	0.25	2.48	0.02			

R²=0.76, Adjusted R = 0.72, D.W = 1.78

According to the data, both the internal and exterior corporate images positively and substantially influenced organizational identification ($t=2.99$, $p=0.00$; and $t=2.48$, $p=0.00$, respectively). Additionally, the findings indicate that organizational identity was influenced more by internal corporate image ($\beta=0.68$) than by outward corporate image ($\beta=0.61$). The R square is calculated to ascertain the strength of connection between the dependent variable and independent variables, with the result showing that ($R^2 = 0.76$). This means that organizational identity accounted for around 76% of the corporate image (internal and external).

The Durbin Watson statistics was performed to determine if autocorrelation existed in our model. $D-W=1.78$ in the model's above computation. This is demonstrated by the absence of autocorrelation in our model, which makes it conclusive. The F-statistic was calculated to see if there was a significant correlation between the dependent and independent variables. There is a significant difference between the dependent variables' values and the predictors' values since the model's $F=10.89$ is higher than the critical F of 5.11. Thus, organizational identity is substantially influenced by corporate image (internal and external). The null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the connection between organizational identification and corporate image. The findings confirmed the theories to the letter. An additional investigation supported the conclusion that organizational identity accounts for the connection between corporate imagery. The study found that workers' perceptions of the external business image boost organizational identification. This is in line with Ashforth et al. (2008)'s assertion that a high level of identification is noteworthy in terms of its correlation with positive organizational behaviors. In this regard, the advantages of employee identification with their organization have been emphasized at both the individual and organizational levels. Similar to Ellis (2008), reported significant correlations between additional-role behavior and support and participation into job factors. They also found a relationship between organizational identification and organizational engagement,

determined a relationship between identification and job satisfaction, and determined a relationship between that and the desire to continue in one's current position and discontinuance.

The second hypothesis demonstrated that when employees' perceptions of their internal company image improve, so does their organizational affiliation. According to Bartel (2001), organizational choices are made through teamwork and collaboration in order to improve organizational effectiveness. Additionally, as reported by March, Simon, and McGregor and cited by Ashforth et al. (2008), organizational identification merges individual and organizational goals, improves harmony, and increases external image.

According to evidence, organizational identification and corporate image (both internal and external) are closely associated. This is in line with Wiesenfeld et al. (1999)'s assertion that creating a sense of belonging among members of an organization encourages greater organizational loyalty. On the other side, by fostering a sense of safety among the workforce, norms and values are internalized, which increases employees' desire and intention to stay with the company. An important organizational predecessor of organizational identification, according to Ashford and Mael (1996), was the corporate image. Additionally, the researchers noted in their study that one of the benefits of group identification for individuals is to increase the respect that is accorded to them, with employees of well-known companies reporting higher levels of self-respect.

Conclusion

High levels of corporate image perception and organizational identification were identified based on the results. With publicly traded corporations, it was thought that organizational identification levels and corporate image dimensions may be higher. Another analysis came to the conclusion that a rise in the perception of the internal and external corporate image might lead to a rise in organizational identification, and the study hypotheses were thus approved. It was found that the perceived exterior image had a stronger impact on organizational identification than the perceived internal image. In other words, workers' good judgments of the organization's internal policies and procedures increase their sense of organizational affiliation compared to their positive perceptions of the organization's external policies and practices. The results of the study led to the conclusion that there is a strong positive relationship between perceived internal and external image and organizational identity, and that both corporate image's sub-dimensions had a favorable impact on that relationship.

Recommendation

The conclusions lead to the following suggestions:

Future studies might look at whether organizational culture affects the way that corporate image and organizational identification are perceived, if at all.

- Additionally, the importance that employees have on corporate image as well as how well it aligns with their personal beliefs may have an impact on how engaged they are at work. According to their own social responsibility beliefs, an employee who believes their company is prestigious because it practices social responsibility may be more (or less) inclined to report involvement.

- Future studies should examine the link between employer reputation and employee satisfaction while taking other resources—particularly socioeconomic resources—into consideration.

Suggestions for more research

Future studies should also look at the links between organizational identity and various forms of perceived corporate image perceptions (such as social, economic, etc.).

References

- Abratt, R. (1989). A New Approach to the Corporate Image Management Process, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 5(1), 63-76. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.1989.9964088>
- Albert, S., Ashforth, B. E., & Dutton, J. E. (2000). Organizational Identity and Identification: Charting New Waters and Building New Bridges. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), 13-17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMR.2000.2791600>
- Ashforth, B. E., Harrison, S. H., & Corley, K. G. (2008). Identification in organizations: An examination of four fundamental questions. *Journal of Management*, 34, 325–374. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0149206308316059>
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. A. (1998). The power of resistance: Sustaining valued identities. In R. M. Kramer & M. A. Neale (Eds.), *Power and influence in organizations* (pp. 89-120). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483345291.n5>
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. A. (1996). Organizational identity and strategy as a context for the individual. *Advances in Strategic Management*, 13, 19-64.
- Ashforth, B. E., & Mael, F. (1989). Social identity theory and the organization. *Academy of management review*, 14(1), 20-39. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.2307/258189>
- Barich, H., & Kotler, P. (1991). A Framework for Marketing Image Management. *Sloan Management Review*, 32(2), 94-109.
- Bartels, J., Pruyn, A., Jong, M. D., & Joustra, I. (2007). Multiple Organizational Identification Levels and The Impact of Perceived External Prestige and Communication Climate. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 28(2), 173-190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.420>
- Bartel, C. A. (2001). Social Comparisons in Boundary-Spanning Work: Effects of Community Outreach on Members' Organizational Identity and Identification. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 46(3), 379-413. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3094869>
- Boros, A. (2008). *U.S. Patent No. 7,440,751*. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Buchanan, B. (1974). Building organizational commitment: The socialization of managers in work organizations. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 19, 533-546. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391809>
- Cheney, G., Christensen, L. T., Zorn, T. E., & Ganesh, S. (2010). *Organizational Communication in an Age of Globalization: Issues, Reflections, Practices* (2nd ed.). Waveland Press, Inc., USA.
- Dichter, E. (1985). What's in an Image. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 2, 75-81. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb038824>
- Dorgan, J. F., & Schatzkin, A. (1991). *Antioxidant micronutrients in cancer prevention*. Hematol Oncol Clin North Am.
- Dukerich, J. (2016). Organizational Identity and the Undesired Self. In *The Oxford Handbook of Organizational Identity*. Oxford University Press.
- Dutton, J. E., Dukerich, J. M., & Harquail, C. V. (1994). Organizational Images and Member Identification. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 39(2), 239-263. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.2307/2393235>
- Edwards, M. R. (2005). Organizational Identification: A Conceptual and Operational Review, *International Journal of Management Review*, 7(4), 207-230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2005.00114.x>

- Ellis, A. D. (2008). *The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Employee Attitudes and Behaviors*. Arizona State University, books. google.com.tr/books?isbn=0549595872, Erişim Tarihi:13.10.2014.
- Gautam, P. K., Gautam, R. K., Banerjee, S. Chattopadhyaya, M. C., & Pandey, J. D. (2016). *Heavy metals in the environment: fate, transport, toxicity, and remediation technologies*. Nava Science Publishers.
- Gautam, T., Van Dick, R., & Wagner, U. (2004). Organizational Identification and Organizational Commitment: Distinct Aspects of Two Related Concepts. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 7(3), 301-315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-839X.2004.00150.x>
- Gray, E. R., & Smeltzer, L. R. (1985). SMR Forum: Corporate image--An integral part of strategy. *Sloan Management Review (pre-1986)*, 26(4), 73.
- Hall, D.T., B. Schneider, and H.T. Nygren (1970). Personal Factors in Organizational Identification. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 15, 176-190.
- Haslam, S. A., Postmes T., & Ellemers, N. (2003). More than a Metaphor: Organizational Identity Makes Organizational Life Possible. *British Journal of Management*, 14(4), 357-369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8551.2003.00384.x>
- Knippenberg, D. V., & Van Schie, C. M. (2000). Foci and correlates of organizational identification. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(2), 137-147. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317900166949>
- Kose, C. G. (2009). *Orgütsel Ozdeşleşmenin Qahşanlarm Stirekliyileştirme Qabalarma Katkisi: Bir Araştırma, Yaymlanmami?* Yüiksek Lisans Tezi Istanbul Universitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Istanbul.
- Kotter, J. P. (1996). *Leading change*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Lambert, P. R. (1990). Congenital absence of the oval window. *The Laryngoscope*, 100(1), 37-40. <https://doi.org/10.1288/00005537-199001000-00009>
- Lasswell, H. D. (1935). *World politics and personal insecurity*. Free Press.
- Levinson H. (1991). Management by whose objectives? *Harvard Business Review*.
- March, J. G., & Simon, H. A. 1958. *Organizations*. New York: Wiley
- McGregor, D. (1967). *The professional manager*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Miller, V. D., Allen M., Casey M. K., & Jonhson, J. R. (2000). Reconsidering The Organizational Identification Questionnaire. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 13(4), 626-658. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318900134003>
- O'Reilly, C. A., & Chatman, J. (1986). Organizational Commitment and Psychological Attachment: The Effects of Compliance, Identification, and Internalization on Prosocial Behaviour. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), 492-499. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.492>
- Olins, W. (1999). *The New Guide to Identity*. Gower Publishing Limited, Hampshire.
- Pratt, M. G. (1998). To Be or Not to Be?: Central Question in Organizational Identification. In D. A. Whetten & P. C. Godfrey (Eds.), *Identity in Organizations: Building Theory Through Conversation* (pp. 171-207). Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452231495.n6>
- Riketta, M. (2005). Organizational Identification: 'A' Meta-Analysis'k. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 66(2), 358-384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2004.05.005>
- Simon, H. A. (1976). *Administrative Behavior-A Study of Decision-Making Processes in Administrative Organization*. 3rd Edition, Macmillan Publishing Co. Inc., New York.
- Smidts, A., Pruyn, Ad. T. H., & Van Riel, C. B. M. (2001). The Impact of Employee Communication and Perceived External Prestige on Organizational Identification. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(5), 1051-1062. <https://doi.org/10.5465/3069448>
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1985). The Social Identity Theory of Intergroup Behaviour. In S. Worchel & W. G. Austin (Eds.), *Psychology of Intergroup Relations* (2nd Ed.)(pp. 7-24), Nelson Hall, Chicago.
- Tajfel, H. (1982). Social Psychology of Intergroup Relations. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 33, 1-39.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ps.33.020182.000245>

- Tokgöz, E., & Aytemiz Seymen, O. (2011). Örgütsel güven, örgütsel özdeşleşme ve örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışı arasındaki ilişki: Bir devlet hastanesinde araştırma
- Tompkins, P. K., & Cheney, G. (1985). Communication and unobtrusive control in contemporary organizations. *Organizational communication: Traditional themes and new directions*, 13, 179-210.
- Van Knippenberg, D., & Hogg, M. A. (2018). Social identifications in organizational behavior. In D. L. Ferris, R. E. Johnson & C. Sedikides (Eds.), *The self at work: Fundamental theory and research* (pp. 72-90). Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.4324/9781315626543-4>
- Wiesenfeld, B. M., Raghuram, S., & Garud, R. (1999). Communication Patterns as Determinants of Organizational Identification in a Virtual Organization, *Organization Science*, 10(6), 777-790. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.10.6.777>
- Whetten, D. A., & Godfrey, P. C. (Eds.). (1998). *Identity in organizations: Building theory through conversations*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Witting, M. (2006). *Relations Between Organizational Identity, Identification and Organizational Objectives: An Empirical Study in Municipalities*. Erişim. Retrieved: <http://Essay.Utwente.nl/55524/l/Scriptie> Witting. Pdf, 14.09.2014.

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Conflict of Interests

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